

Impact of the use of treated wastewater for irrigation on the physico-chemical quality of soils: A case study from Ain Defla, Algeria

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Abstract

The use of treated wastewater is considered a good alternative for the different agricultural irrigation practices and the sustainable management program for the conservation of water and soil in semi-arid areas. The main objective of this research work is to determine the impacts of the reuse of treated wastewater (TWW) on some soil properties with the collection and analysis of 68 samples from the Ain Defla wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) over a three-year period, under a turf cultivation system. Soil samples were taken at depths ranging from 0 to 20 and 20 to 40 cm and then analyzed for pH, electrical conductivity (EC) and overall mineralization. The results showed large changes, over time, in the chemical properties of the soil due to irrigation with treated wastewater compared to the control, with median pH values varying from 8.12 in 2015 to 8.15 in 2016 and 8.91 in 2017. The pH increased significantly from 8.12 in non-irrigated soil to 8.22 in soil irrigated with treated wastewater. There was a significant difference between the two horizons (8.15 at the surface and 8.24 at depth). The electrical conductivity went from 0.25 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ in 2015 to 0.37 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ in 2016 to drop to 0.15 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and 2017. The electrical conductivity has doubled between the non-irrigated soil (0.14 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) and the irrigated one (0.28 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) while it has not changed between the two horizons (0.27 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ on the surface and 0.24 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ in depth). The results obtained during these three years show that treated wastewater is a main source of increase in mineral salts in the soil which could lead to the degradation of the environment in general and that of the physico-chemical

quality of soil in a particular. Also, it was found that treated wastewater can be a potential source of essential nutrients for plants by accumulation in soils.

Keywords: Irrigation, Physico-chemical, Reuse, Soil, Treated wastewater.

Introduction

The rate of population growth in semi-arid regions is characterized by high consumption of water resources, in a global context marked by climate change and scarcity of rainfall in recent years. Algeria is one of the Mediterranean countries affected by water stress. It is classified in the category of poor countries in this matter. The TWW in agriculture is proving to be one of the solutions likely to solve, even if only partially, the problem of lack of irrigation water in areas marked with low precipitation (Faby and Brissaud, 1997; Eccose, 2001). Among the wastewater treatment plants operated by the National Sanitation Office (ONA) across the 43 wilayas, there are just a few plants that are concerned with the reuse of TWW in agriculture. In 2011, the volume reused is estimated at 17 million m³/year, in order to irrigate more than 10,000 hectares of agricultural area MRE (2012). Indeed, this potential for re-using TWW for agricultural purposes has undergone significant development, where approximately 17 million m³ were recorded in 2011, approximately 45 million m³ in 2012 and 300 million m³ in 2014 (MRE, 2012; ONA, 2014). Irrigation with TWW can affect the physicochemical properties of soils (Lado and Ben-Hur, 2009; Levy, 2011; Levy et al., 2011; Feigin et al., 2012; Chen et al., 2004; Tarchouna et al., 2010), and agricultural production Yadav et al. (2002). These impacts depend not only on the quality of the irrigation water but also on the frequency of use of the TWW used, the duration of the irrigation and the local climate (season). The study that we present is a contribution to the evaluation of the impact of the short, medium and long terms of irrigation with treated wastewater from the WWTP at the level of the irrigated perimeter of Ain Defla region characterized by well-defined climatic conditions. The objective of our study is to characterize in more detail the state of the soils after three years of irrigation by TWW and to assess the impact of these waters on the physicochemical properties of the soil such as sodicity and alkalinity at two different depths.

Materials and Methods

The study site is located in the WWTP, located in the town of Ain Defla, 5 km northeast of the capital of the wilaya. The low load activated sludge plant has an area of 5 hectares and a treatment capacity of 12,900 m³/day. The climate of the region is Mediterranean with an average annual rainfall of 420 mm and the average air temperature is 20 °C.

The study was carried out between September 2015 and September 2017 during three years (2015, 2016, and 2017) on a field covered by grass. During each year, we followed the samples and analyzes of the soil from the point of view of physicochemical parameters (quality and quantity).

To assess the impacts of TWW on the physico-chemical properties of the soil, we chose two plots: a plot not irrigated by TWW but having precipitation water as an irrigation source and a plot irrigated with TWW. No fertilizer was applied in the two plots.

Water sampling and analysis

The water samples were taken directly at the exit of the station after the treatments carried out by the WWTP. These collected waters were sampled in tightly closed plastic bottles, named by codes and kept in a cooler until the time of analysis. The physicochemical analyzes were carried out at the level of the laboratories of the WWTP, the Algerienne des Eaux (ADE), the National Observatory of the Environment and Sustainable Development (ONEDD) of Ain Defla and the Laboratory of Agricultural Production and Sustainable Valuation of Natural Resources (PRAVDURN) of the University of Khemis Miliana.

The irrigation water was analyzed monthly for the parameters pH, electrical conductivity (EC), suspended solids (SS), biological oxygen demand (BOD₅), chemical oxygen demand (COD), total nitrogen (N_T), nitrate (NO₃⁻), nitrite (NO₂⁻), and total phosphorus (P_T) and once a year for trace elements and major elements such as Cr, Zn, Ni, Pb, Mg, K, Ca, Cl, and Na. The analyzes were carried out according to the standards recommended by ISO and AFNOR or those approved Rodier (1996). The sodium adsorption rate (SAR) and the exchangeable sodium rate (ESP) were calculated using the following standard equations:

$$SAR = Na^+ / [(Ca^{+2} + Mg^{+2}) / 2]^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

$$ESP = [Na^+ / [(Ca^{+2} + Mg^{+2} + Na^+ + K^+)]] * 100 \quad (2)$$

Irrigation protocol

Irrigation was carried out using a gravity-fed irrigation system, the plot irrigated by TWW was more than 20 m from the non-irrigated one to avoid any contamination. The volume of irrigation water and the frequency of application are two critical factors in controlling the impact of TWW on soil properties. Their irrigation is carried out by the same irrigation system during the three years with a constant flow of 1,800 l/h, or a total of 43,200 liters of water per day. The plot is irrigated three times a week during summer and once during spring and autumn.

Soil sampling and analysis

The soil samples were taken in accordance with internationally recommended procedures (AFNOR NF x31-100) in September 2015 and 2016, after the summer season and in March 2017 after the winter season. Structural stability analyzes were performed in September 2017. Soil samples were taken from the field using an agricultural auger in two different horizons (0-20 and 20-40 cm) 30 samples for the plot irrigated by TWW and 4 samples for the plot not irrigated. The soil samples were stored in poly bags and marked with sampling details and transferred to the laboratory for testing. The soil was air dried for a week and then sieved. The physical analysis of the soil, to determine the textural classes of the soil using the "Robinson's pipette"

method, complies with standards (*NEN5357 and ISO/DIS 11277*). The structural stability was determined by slow wetting method Bissonnais, Souder (1995). Acidity and salinity of the soil were evaluated by determining the pH and EC at 25 °C on a soil extract (1/2.5 and 1/5 Soil/Water) using a pH meter and a conductivity meter (WTW multi 340i). Organic matter (OM) was determined by the weight loss method using an oven at 375 °C for 16 hours Moreno et al. (2001). Sodium (Na) and potassium (K) were determined on soil extract using an IC9200 flame photometer (JENWAY PFP7). Chloride (Cl) was determined by the titrimetric method with silver nitrate solution Karaivazoglou et al. (2005). Calcium (Ca) and magnesium (Mg) in soil extracts were determined by the EDTA method Pauwels et al. (1992). Phosphorus (P) was determined using a spectrophotometer (860 nm) by the Olsen method Nelson, Sommers (1982). Total nitrogen was determined by dry combustion (*Elemental analysis / FN ISO; 13878*). The sodium adsorption rate (SAR) Richards (1954) and the exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) were expressed in cmol/kg and calculated using formulas (1) and (2).

Statistical analyses

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) would be used to test the effects of the three factors (years, irrigation, and depths) on soil properties if data followed normal distribution and had constant variances. However, Shapiro-Wilk test showed the lack of normality of data while the Levene test showed their heteroscedasticity. Therefore, nonparametric methods were used instead. Mann-Whitney test was used to evaluate the effect of the two levels factors (irrigation and depths) while the Kruskal-Wallis test was used to evaluate the effect of the three level factor (years). For the latter, in cases of significant differences, pairwise comparisons were done using the Dunn-Bonferroni posthoc test. Median values should be reported instead of mean values which are given just for comparison.

Results and Discussion

Physicochemical properties of TWW

The physicochemical characteristics of irrigation water (TWW) were monitored during the three years (2015, 2016, and 2017) while heavy metals were only monitored during 2015. Table 1, summarizes the results obtained during these years by indicating the limit values of the monitoring parameters with a comparison with the standards for the reuse of treated wastewater according to the FAO (1985), the Algerian Executive Decree (2012) and the tolerant concentration limits by the European Commission for water irrigation systems (*Catchment Management Agencies, recommendation 91-692 (CMA)*).

Table 1. Results of physicochemical and heavy metals analyses of TWW (2015-2017).

Parameter	Unit	2015		2016		2017		Norms	
		F	Mean	F	Mean	F	Mean	JORA 2012	OMS/FAO/CMA
T	°C	12	21.35	12	20.80	12	20.79	<30	-
pH	/	12	7.72	12	7.64	12	7.86	6.5-8.5*	6.5-8.5**
EC	µS/cm	12	1.97	12	1.86	12	1.87	<3*	3**
SAR	/	1	2.18	1	3.74	1	2.31		6-12***
HCO ₃ ⁻	mg/l	1	294.3	1	346.2	1	305	-	8.5 meq/l
SO ₄ ²⁻	mg/l	1	225.6	1	281.3	1	243	-	250***
N total	mg/l	12	7.9	12	6.34	12	8.36	50*	30**
N-NO ₃ ⁻	mg/l	12	6.85	12	4.37	12	6.95	30*	5**
N-NO ₂ ⁻	mg/l	12	0.13	12	0.07	12	0.15	-	1**
N-NH ₄ ⁺	mg/l	12	0.84	12	3.05	12	2.02	5***	2**
P total	mg/l	12	2.6	12	3.24	12	2.26	-	-
P-PO ₄ ³⁻	mg/l	12	4.27	12	7.04	12	7	5***	0,94*
K	mg/l	1	10.5	1	14.5	1	9.8	-	12***
Na	mg/l	1	115.4	1	221.3	1	123	-	150***
Ca	mg/l	1	148	1	189.5	1	156	-	50***
Mg	mg/l	1	38.88	1	45.6	1	34.06	-	50***
Cl	mg/l	1	289.4	1	281.3	1	300.68	10 meq/l	200***
SS	mg/l	12	20.44	12	75.25	12	16.92	30*	30**
DBO	mg/l	12	6.7	12	12.71	12	8.87	30	10**
DCO	mg/l	12	30.55	12	32.76	12	29.27	90	40**
Pb	mg/l	1	<0.2	-	-	-	-	-	5**
Ni	mg/l	1	<0.2	-	-	-	-	-	0,2**
Fe	mg/l	1	<0.2	-	-	-	-	-	5**
Cu	mg/l	1	<0.1	-	-	-	-	-	0,2**
Zn	mg/l	1	<0.03	-	-	-	-	-	2**
Cr	mg/l	1	<0.2	-	-	-	-	-	0,1**

*** CMA 91-692. ** FAO (1985). * OMS (1989).

F: frequency of analyzes; *EC*: electrical conductivity; *SS*: suspended solids; *COD*: chemical oxygen demand; *BOD*: biochemical oxygen demand; *SAR*: sodium adsorption rate. *T*: temperature.

The average pH of TWW, for the three years, is within the standards, between 6.5 and 8.5 JORA (2012), and is acceptable because it is in the range based on FAO standards (Ayers and Westcot, 1985; Pescod, 1992). The EC ranges from 1.87 to 1.97 µS/cm, indicating a light to moderate level of salinity Pescod (1992). These values remain below the limit value of 3 µS/cm for use in irrigation JORA (2012) and there is no risk for the physical properties of the soil Ayers, Westcot (1985). The concentration of Cl varies between 281.3 and 300.68 mg/l, this is an acceptable concentration for surface irrigation (Boulahbal, 2011; Ayers and Westcot, 1985).

The COD and BOD₅ are in the Algerian standards for the reuse of TWW in irrigation JORA (2012). The high level of SS for 2016 is due to the loss of sludge from the clarifier, this value remains above the acceptable range based on the standards (JORA, 2012; Ayers and Westcot, 1985). In general, the contents of Ca, K, Na, Mg, and NH₄ are variable over the years but we can indicate that, according to the standards, SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻, HCO₃⁻, and P show no change in the nature of the

irrigation water. In addition, the concentration of heavy metals is low and lower than the standard for irrigation water (JORA, 2012; Ayers and Westcot, 1985), the element most represented is chromium with a content of less than 0.2 mg/l. These concentrations will have no toxic effect on soil characteristics Godfrin, Van Bladel (1990).

Effects of TWW on soil properties

Soil texture

Textural analysis shows that the two irrigated plots have high sand contents compared to the other two fractions (Table 2).

Table 2. *Physical properties of the soil (Soil texture) in the experimental site.*

Plot	Depth	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	Texture
Irrigated	0-20 cm	61.5	11.5	27.0	Sandy clay loam
	20-40 cm	47.5	20.8	31.7	Sandy clay loam
Non irrigated	0-20 cm	54.0	16.0	30.0	Sandy clay loam
	20-40 cm	55.5	13.5	31.0	Sandy clay loam

Soil pH

The results of the effects of years, depths, and irrigations with TWW on the chemical properties of the soil are shown in Tables 3 to 5. Since the distributions of these properties are not normal, the results will be discussed based on median values which are robust to extreme values instead of mean values which are too sensitive to them and hypothesis testing relying on non-parametric methods.

The median pH values of soils irrigated by TWW vary from 8.12 (2005) to 8.91 (2007) (Table 3), these values classify the soils between moderately and strongly alkaline according to the American classification USDA Staff (1993). This could be mainly due to higher concentrations, over time, of cations in wastewater used in basic irrigation which led to an increase in soil pH Gharaibeh et al. (2016). This indicates that three years of TWW irrigation led to a significant increase in pH between years (Table 3), between horizons (median values of 8.15 and 8.24 for surface and in depth) (Table 4) and between irrigation water types with a median of 8.22 in the irrigated plot and 8.12 in the control plot (Table 5). This result is similar to other studies (Mancino and Pepper, 1992; Tarchouna et al., 2010; Cromer et al., 1984) which reported that irrigation with TWW increased pH due to the textural nature of the soil which is a fundamental factor to determine the acidity of the soil, which allows the salts to be leached in depth. The use of TWW in irrigation can have negative effects on the chemical quality of the soil (Kiziloglu et al., 2007; Mutengu et al., 2007).

Table 3. Results for years. NS: not significant at the 0.05 level. Years with different letters are significantly different following the Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc test.

Soil property / Year	Mean			Median			Significance
	2015	2016	2017	2015	2016	2017	
P	17.05	19.46	10.00	12.84 a	18.79 a	9.00 b	0
Mg	20.07	21.37	20.05	20.30 b	22.30 a	20.16 b	0.039
Na	1.95	2.18	2.45	1.98 a	2.03 a	2.33 b	0.008
K	8.76	9.57	12.77	8.68 c	9.49 b	12.45 a	0
Nt	3.11	0.77	0.08	1.46 a	0.69 a	0.08 b	0
Ca	249.43	254.32	247.79	248.40 b	252.45 a	248.58 b	0
Cl	34.51	84.88	81.23	26.98 b	88.7 a	80.81 a	0
pH	8.09	8.15	8.92	8.12 b	8.15 b	8.91 a	0
EC	0.25	0.37	0.15	0.24 b	0.40 a	0.13 c	0
OM	1.29	1.40	1.38	1.07	1.22	1.41	NS
SAR	0.17	0.19	0.20	0.17 b	0.18 b	0.19 a	0
ESP	0.69	0.76	0.84	0.70 b	0.72 b	0.77 a	0

Table 4. Results for depths. NS: not significant at the 0.05 level.

Soil property / Depth	Mean		Median		Significance
	0-20 cm	20-40 cm	0-20 cm	20-40 cm	
P	14.67	16.57	12.00	13.31	NS
Mg	21.41	19.52	22.20	20.09	0.001
Na	2.10	2.27	2.03	2.07	NS
K	10.11	10.43	9.47	9.46	NS
Nt	0.55	1.93	0.19	0.29	NS
Ca	248.27	252.90	248.40	251.35	NS
Cl	84.76	51.02	83.20	48.28	0
pH	8.29	8.37	8.15	8.24	0.01
EC	0.26	0.27	0.27	0.24	NS
OM	1.39	1.33	1.25	1.10	NS
SAR	0.18	0.19	0.18	0.17	0
ESP	0.76	0.78	0.73	0.70	0

Table 5. Results for irrigation. NS: not significant at the 0.05 level.

Soil property / Treatment	Mean		Median		Significance
	EUT	NI	EUT	NI	
P	17.07	6.42	13.60	7.70	0
Mg	21.36	14.42	21.22	14.73	0
Na	2.26	1.62	2.08	1.60	0
K	10.34	9.77	9.54	8.91	NS
N _t	1.42	0.10	0.54	0.10	0.005
Ca	250.96	246.60	251.10	245.85	0.002
Cl	71.48	44.11	62.50	27.00	0
pH	8.35	8.17	8.22	8.12	0.018
EC	0.28	0.14	0.28	0.14	0
OM	1.42	0.89	1.26	0.95	0
SAR	0.19	0.14	0.18	0.15	NS
ESP	0.80	0.61	0.75	0.61	NS

Soil salinity

There is a significant difference between the years concerning the EC of the TWW irrigated soil solution with the highest median value in 2016 (0.40 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) and the lowest in 2017 (0.13 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) (Table 3). The decrease in EC in 2017 may be explained by climatic conditions such as seasonal fall and winter precipitation which was sufficient to ensure dilution and migration to depth of salts accumulated during the summer season Melgar et al., (2009). There is no significant difference between the two horizons (0.27 and 0.24 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) (Table 4). In addition, there is a significant difference between irrigation with TWW and non-irrigation because irrigation doubled the median value of EC (0.28 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ vs. 0.14 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) (Table 5). Similar results have been reported (Jahantigh, 2008; Gil and Ulloa, 1997; Galavi et al., 2010; Khai et al., 2016; Massena, 2001; Xanthoulis et al., 1998). In all cases, the values obtained allow us to consider the soils as unsalted according to the recommended limits Mathieu et al. (2003), and they are below the salinity threshold of 4 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. However, irrigation with TWW could, over time, cause salinization problems linked to the degradation of the physico-chemical properties of the soil.

Organic matter

The median values of OM, although they increase with the years, do not differ significantly (Table 3) with a little more in surface compared to in depth with the difference not being significant (Table 4). On the other hand, there is a significant difference between the irrigated plot (1.26%) and the control one (0.95%) (Table 5). Similar results were found for years (Kiziloglu et al., 2007; Manas et al., 2009) but different for depths (Bedbabis et al., 2014, 2015; Jueschke et al., 2008; Tarchouna et al., 2010). The decrease in OM values measured in the surface layer in 2017 is probably the consequence of low volume of suspended solids. Some studies have shown that the increase in OM was temporary because it is rapidly mineralized by soil microorganisms (Mechri et al., 2007; Di Serio et al., 2008).

Ionic composition of the soil solution

The non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test indicates a significant difference between years for all seven ions (Table 3) and the Mann-Whitney test indicates a significant difference between the use or not of TWW for irrigation for all ions except K (Table 5); however, the Mann-Whitney test indicated significant differences between the two depths only for Mg and Cl (Table 4). The trend over the years is not the same for all ions. Thus, there is an ever increase over the years for Na and K while there was an increase in 2016 followed by a decrease in 2017 for P, Mg, Ca, and Cl; on the other hand, there was a continuous decrease for Nt (Table 3). For the depths, we notice a decrease between the surface and in depth for the two ions Mg and Cl (Table 4). The same behavior as the previous one is also found for the use of TWW with an increase from the control plot to the irrigated one (Table 5).

The results showed that the quantities of Na in the plots irrigated with TWW increased significantly over time from 1.95 (2015) to 2.45 mg/Kg (2017). Such a result has been found elsewhere Halliwell et al. (2001). For Cl, the concentration increased from 34.51 (2015) to 81.23 mg/Kg (2017). Even if the water used has a low concentration of Cl, it caused a significant variation in the accumulation of Cl in the plot irrigated by TWW Rengasamy, (2010), with a low accumulation of Na for the depths of 2.10 mg/Kg (in surface) and 2.27 mg/Kg in (in depth) (Table 4). Such a result was found in another study Halliwell et al. (2001), on the other hand, there was a more significant Cl leaching towards the depth (51.02 mg/Kg) (Table 4). Sodium is one of the most serious specific toxic ions of concern. It is reported that sodium directly affects the availability of crop water and causes unfavorable physicochemical changes in the soil (Richards, 1954; Aubert, 1983; Tessier, 1984), especially in soil structure. It has the ability to disperse soil, which reduces permeability, lowers shear strength and increases compressibility (Chang et al., 2005; Al-Jasser, 2011), and negatively affects plant growth (Shaheen et al., 2013; Shahbaz et al., 2011; Pereira et al., 2011).

The median values of Ca and Mg were higher in soils irrigated by TWW in 2016. This accumulation indicates that the adsorption of these elements on the exchangeable complex was greater than the uptake by plants Bedbabis et al. (2014), and depending on climatic conditions, can also be explained by the high concentration in TWW during the irrigation period (Table 1). At the end of the treatment period (2017), a significant decrease in Ca and Mg was observed, this could be due to rain Laribi, Alzubaidi (2007). In this context, it is possible to conclude that TWW did not promote a rapid increase in the Ca content in the soil and also the migration to the depth is not significant Urbano et al. (2015), on the other hand, the migration of Mg to depth is significant.

Median K values ranged from 8.68 mg/kg (2015) to 12.45 mg/kg (2017) with a significant increase over time (Table 3). This increase was directly caused by the K content in the irrigation water and also the density of vegetation covers present during the sampling time. These results are in agreement with others (Emongor and Ramolemana, 2004; Heidarpour et al., 2007; Arienzo et al., 2009). By comparing these concentrations with the standards, these soils are very poor Riquier (1966).

Monitoring K shows no significant change after irrigation (Table 5) (Bazza and Xanthoulis, 2003; Mouhanni et al., 2011). Stability between horizons was probably a consequence of the uptake or displacement of K from the soil solution to the plant because the K element did not move quickly in the soil profile Nasini et al. (2013). However, the presence of K in high concentration can have several economic advantages by reducing the use of fertilizers Di Serio et al. (2008).

The results obtained for Nt and P during the three years reveal a significant decrease recorded at the end of the experiment (2017) (Table 3), with a slight increase in P between the first two years irrigated by TWW of 17.05 mg/Kg (2015) and 19.46 mg/Kg (2016). This is an indication that TWW irrigation increased soil P (Akponikpè et al., 2011; Emongor and Ramolemana, 2004; Heidarpour et al., 2007). Despite the high Nt concentration of TWW, there was a significant decrease in the total nitrogen content during the treatment period due to subsequent consumption by the presence of grass since Nt and P are considered important nutrients for plant growth (Mouhanni et al., 2011; Sacks and Bernstein, 2011; López-Piñeiro et al., 2008) and soil wiping by rainwater Boulahbal (2011). It is observed that the concentrations of Nt and P in the surface layer are lower than those in depth, so there was an non significant leaching in the layers probably due to the method of irrigation and the soil capacity of adsorption (Miller et al., 1980; Jnab et al., 2001; Oron et al., 1992).

ESP and SAR.

Regarding ESP and SAR, there were significant differences between years (Table 3) and depths (Table 4) but not between the use or not of TWW for irrigation (Table 5). In this study, the median values of ESP and SAR in soils irrigated by TWW reveal an increase recorded at the end of the experiment (2017) (Table 3). A similar result has been found in other studies (Gharaibeh et al., 2007; Warrington et al., 2007; Sou et al., 2013; Galavi et al., 2010). The increase in ESP corresponds to a linear increase in the SAR values of the plot irrigated by TWW (Harron et al., 1983; Bower, 1959; Gharaibeh et al., 2016). In all cases, all the measured values are lower than the limit for a soil to be considered sodic when they present a SAR greater than 13% or an ESP greater than 15% (Sumner, 1993; Legros, 2007; Richards, 1954). However, when monitoring the work, the values of ESP and SAR increase significantly in depth for the plot irrigated with TWW. These results are in agreement with several research works Stevens et al. (2003). The evolution of SAR and ESP at depth is linked to the leaching of salts between irrigation periods. In such contexts, the extent of salt leaching from soils is known to be related to salt solubility, irrigation volume, rate of ion migration, and soil permeability (Tedeschi and Dell'Aquila, 2005; Levy et al., 2003). ESP and SAR values did not indicate saturation of the soil exchange complex with sodium ions, but there are other indicators responsible for ESP and SAR. This result showed that Na accumulation is low in soils irrigated by TWW. Similar results were found Urbano et al. (2015). However, increasing the concentrations of bicarbonates in irrigation water (TWW), with an average value of 315 mg/l due to their combination with Ca or Mg ions, leads to the formation of a precipitate of Ca or Mg carbonate in the soil, and with an average chloride content of 290 mg/l in irrigation water (TWW). This causes increased Na content and SAR (Ayers and

Westcot, 1985; Feigin et al., 2012). No significant difference was observed between the irrigated plot and the control plot, there is a small increase for the soils irrigated by TWW compared to the control soil. It could be postulated from the duration of treatment by TWW (three years) and by the lower OM concentration in the treated soils can lead to complexation of cations which has an important role in the increase or the decrease of the ESP and SAR (Oster and Rhoades, 2018; Metzger et al., 1983; Feigin et al., 1991).

Structural stability of soil

Structural stability is an important characteristic of soil and there are several factors responsible for the degradation of aggregate stability (Whelan et al., 1995; Saidi et al., 1999; Diaz-Zorita et al., 2002). Irrigation with TWW in arid and semi-arid regions poses unique and unknown problems for the farming community, one of which is the possible degradation of soil structure and their stability.

* PI: Plot irrigated by TWW. PNI: Plot not irrigated.

Fig. 1. Effects of TWW irrigation on soil structural stability.

The likely risks of adverse changes in soil structure and stability after irrigation with TWW may arise from higher levels of dissolved organic matter, suspended matter, sodium adsorption rate (SAR) and soil salinity of TWW Levy (2011). To assess the structural stability at the level of the irrigated and non-irrigated soils by TWW, two different years were chosen: the first sample was taken in September 2016 for the two plots and after one year of irrigation by TWW, a second sample was taken in the same plot. The recorded results show stabilization in the soil aggregates with an MWD of 0.55 and 0.59 mm compared to 1.34 and 1.20 mm for the non-irrigated plot (Fig. 1). In our case, the soil is unstable Bissonnais, Souder (1995). In this study, the stability of soils irrigated by TWW was lower than that of non-irrigated soils due to the increase in ESP and SAR. There is a significant difference in the structural stability between the plots irrigated by TWW and those not irrigated. There appears to be no change in structural stability during the TWW irrigation times; the likely conditions preventing the change would be that long-term irrigation with TWW has resulted in some deterioration of stability and coarse and medium textured soils (<25% clay) irrigated with TWW create conditions favoring the dispersal of clay by

increasing sodicity, which seems to play only a minor role in determining the stability of aggregates Kemper, Koch (1966), and also related to the intensity of turf cultivation Levy et al. (2006).

Conclusion

The reuse of TWW in semi-arid regions, such as Ain Defla (Algeria), is a key strategy to protect the sustainability of natural water resources. From an environmental point of view, in general and specifically pedological, irrigation by TWW has led to a modification in the characteristics of the soil. The main objective of this work was to examine the impacts of treated wastewater on the physicochemical characteristics of soils. The analyzes performed as a function of time result in much more significant changes in the chemical compositions of the soil. There is an increase in pH and electrical conductivity in the soil profile, depending on irrigation water concentrations (TWW) and climatic conditions. At the same time, there is a moderate increase for major elements such as Na, P, K, Ca, and Mg; however, these concentrations are reduced due to several factors, including climate (precipitation), irrigation water ion concentration (TWW), and the presence of vegetation cover, as is the case with total nitrogen which is considered among the main nutrients of plants. Also, a significant increase with time and frequency of TWW irrigation was observed for SAR and ESP. Although we did not notice any change in the physical appearance of the soil such as structural stability, this is due to the short period of irrigation, hence the impact of seasonal TWW irrigation to see variations in chemical appearance and long-term for the physical aspect of the soil. We should not forget, either, the season and the time of irrigation, the irrigation system, the frequency of irrigation and the quality of irrigation water which are the primary factors that determine the risk of physical and chemical degradation of soil. Therefore, it is not possible to use TWW as an alternative source of irrigation water without considering the factors mentioned above.

Contributions of authors

Rata Y and **Douaoui A** designed and performed the experiments, performed the statistical analysis and also wrote the original manuscript. **Douaoui A**, **Rata M**, and **Douaoui A** reviewed the manuscript. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

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